

LINGUISTICS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

Radjabova Jayron Ikram qizi

EFL teacher of English Department at Tashkent State University
of Uzbek Language and Literature
radjabovajayron99@gmail.com

Abstract: The article states that language stands out among other phenomena reality. Some branches of linguistics are listed.

Key words: linguistics, English, student, teacher, higher education institution.

When learning any language, it is important to pay attention to a number of its components. This also applies linguistics. The term linguistics comes from the Latin word *lingua*, which means "language". Therefore, linguistics is the science that studies language. It gives information about what makes it stand out language among other phenomena of reality, what are its elements and units, how and what changes occur in the language. Linguistics of the English language studies the structures and patterns of a given language, its functioning and development, and also compares with others languages to identify connections with it.

Linguistics can be general or specific. General linguistics – examines, explores and compares all languages of the world as a whole. Particular linguistics considers only one specific language. In our case, English. Linguistics is divided into scientific linguistics and practical linguistics. Most often, linguistics means scientific linguistics. Linguistics is part of semiotics as the science of signs. So, linguistics is generalization of all sciences about language. Phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, stylistics and others are her branches. It is impossible to list everything that linguistics includes. Speaking about grammar, for example, we can clearly say that it has two subsections: morphology and syntax, which in turn have their own ramifications. They are all parts linguistics. Language is not given to the linguist through direct observation; only facts

of speech or linguistic phenomena, that is, speech acts of native speakers of a living language along with their texts or language material. Linguistics involves observation; registration and description of speech facts; hypothesizing to explain these facts; formulation of hypotheses in the form of theories and models describing language; their experimental verification and refutation; predicting speech behavior.

Empirical linguistics obtains linguistic data in two ways. First: method experiment - observation of the behavior of speakers of living dialects. Second way: surgery philological methods, collecting materials from written languages and interacting with philology, which studies written monuments in their cultural and historical connections. Theoretical linguistics studies the laws of language and formulates them in the form of theories. She can be either descriptive. The language studied by a linguist is an object language, and the language in which a theory is formulated is metalanguage. Metatexts are created in a metalanguage - these are grammars, dictionaries, linguistic atlases, maps geographical distribution of languages, language textbooks, phrase books, etc. You can't say only about languages, but also about language in general, since the languages of the world have much in common. Private Linguistics studies a single language, a group of related languages, or a pair of contacting languages. The study of common features of all languages empirically and deductively, general patterns functioning of language, general linguistics is engaged in the development of methods for studying language. Part of it is a typology that compares different languages regardless of the degree of their relationship and drawing conclusions about language in general. Monolingual linguistics is limited to the description of one language, but can distinguish different linguistic subsystems within it and study the relationships between them. Diachronic linguistics compares different time periods in the history of a language. External Linguistics describes language in all its diversity of social variants and functions. Internal linguistics considers language as a homogeneous code, where the description can be focused on written and oral speech; can only describe a system of laws operating in all varieties of the language or include rules for choosing between variants depending on from extralinguistic factors. The

term linguistics comes from the Latin word *lingua*, which means "language". Therefore, linguistics is the science that studies language. It provides information about what distinguishes language from other phenomena of reality, what its elements and units are, how and what changes occur in language. Linguistics of the English language - studies the structures and patterns of the English language, its functioning and development, and also compares with other languages to identify connections with it.

Linguistics can be general or specific. General - examines, explores and compares all languages of the world as a whole. Linguistics of the English language is a particular linguistics that deals with one specific language. In the broad sense of the word, linguistics is divided into scientific and practical. Most often, linguistics refers to scientific linguistics. Linguistics is part of semiotics as the science of signs. Linguistic scientists are professionally engaged in linguistics.

Linguistics is a generalization of all sciences about language. Phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, stylistics, etc. are branches of linguistics. It is impossible to list everything that linguistics includes because it includes everything. Some sciences are so closely intertwined with each other that their differences are blurred, they can be subsidiary to several other sciences at the same time, and therefore it is not possible to talk about any systematicity. Speaking about grammar, for example, we can clearly say that it has two subsections: morphology and syntax, which in turn have their own branches. They are all parts of linguistics. Linguistics involves observation; registration and description of speech facts; developing hypotheses to explain these facts; formulation of hypotheses in the form of theories and models describing language; their experimental verification and refutation; predicting speech behavior. The explanation of facts can be internal through linguistic facts, or external through physiological, psychological, logical or social facts. Being a humanitarian science, linguistics does not always distinguish the subject of knowledge (the psyche of the linguist) from the object of knowledge (the language being studied). People with subtle linguistic intuition and heightened linguistic reflection often become linguists.

We can talk not only about “languages,” but also about “Language” in general, since the languages of the world have much in common. Special linguistics studies a single language, a group of related languages, or a pair of contacting languages. General - common features of all languages, both empirically and deductively, exploring the general patterns of language functioning, developing methods for studying language and giving a scientific definition of linguistic concepts. Part of general linguistics is typology, which compares different languages regardless of the degree of their relationship and draws conclusions about language in general. It identifies and formulates linguistic universals, i.e. hypotheses applicable to most of the described languages of the world. Thus, diachronic linguistics compares different time slices in the history of a language, identifying losses and innovations; dialectology compares its territorial variants, identifying their distinctive features; stylistics compares different functional varieties of language, identifying similarities and differences between them, etc. External linguistics describes: language in all the diversity of its social variants and functions; the dependence of the structure of the language on the social stratum to which the speaker belongs, on his regional affiliation and on the communicative situation of the interlocutors. Internal linguistics abstracts from this dependence by considering language as a homogeneous code. The description can be focused on written and oral speech; may be limited only to the “correct” language, or also take into account various deviations from it; can describe only a system of patterns that operate in all varieties of language, or also include rules for choosing between options depending on extra-linguistic factors.

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